

Organically modified superhydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ – Synthesis, characterization, absorption and photoluminescence behaviour

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Abstract : Synthesis of superhydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ with complex morphologies under the influence of lauric acid in methanol medium was investigated. Lauric acid directed the transformation of thermodynamically stable broken sponge-like calcite CaCO_3 to ellipsoid-like vaterite. Further, flower shaped amorphous $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ resulted after doping the lanthanide elements to CaCO_3 . The morphology, composition and phases of the synthesized compounds was characterized with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Water contact angle of 140° indicates superhydrophobic behavior of lauric acid modified CaCO_3 . More importantly, these materials also displayed high absorption for oils, dyes and genotoxic solvents such as xylene and toluene. The room temperature photoluminescence (PL) measurements of $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ showed emission at 484 nm (blue) and 545 nm (green), respectively.

Keywords : Carbonates, lauric acid, morphology, superhydrophobicity, photoluminescence.

Introduction

Calcium carbonate has been extensively studied as model biomineral which exists in three crystalline forms such as calcite, aragonite and vaterite^{1,2}. Calcium carbonate finds wide variety of applications in industry, environmental remediation and synthesis of metal oxides³. Control of crystal growth via bio-inspired route is an attractive approach for production of complex mineral morphologies with novel properties^{1,4,5}. It is well known that organic additives with carboxylic acid functional groups can direct the phase and morphology of calcium carbonate⁶⁻⁹. Shape controlled synthesis of composite inorganic materials, with inorganic-organic interface, is an emerging soft chemical approach. Surface of inorganic crystals are often modified by a variety of fatty acids through chemisorption for various technological applications¹⁰⁻¹². Adsorption of hydrophobic solvents is one of them. Many studies have shown that the surface coated hydrophobic metal carbonates also exhibit the property of removing oils and coloured dyes¹³⁻¹⁶.

Photoluminescence is an important optical phenomenon which involve absorption of energy and subsequent emission of light. Emission of high quality colour lumi-

nescence is an attractive feature of lanthanide elements doped into host lattices¹⁷. In general, metal oxides, phosphates, vanadates and silicates act as conventional host lattices for rare-earth elements¹⁸. Recently CaCO_3 also used as host material for lanthanide elements, Tb^{3+} and Eu^{3+} , for making inorganic phosphors¹⁹. In addition to luminescence behaviour, lanthanide elements play an important role as a dopant in stabilizing the phases and morphology of calcium carbonate^{20,21}.

In this study, production of superhydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ in presence of lauric acid was investigated. In particular, the influence of lauric acid and lanthanide dopants on morphology, absorption and luminescent properties were explored.

Results and discussion

Morphology and phase identification :

The influence of lauric acid at variable concentrations (mole ratio $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{LA}] = 100, 50, 10$) on phase and morphology of CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ was examined. Fig. 1 shows the formation of CaCO_3 calcite phase with broken sponge-like morphology in control experiments i.e. without addition of crystal growth modi-

Fig. 1. SEM images of CaCO₃ produced in (a) control experiments and (b) presence of lauric acid (mole ratios [M]/[L] = 100).

fier, lauric acid. Trace amount of vaterite phase was also observed along with the major phase of calcite. In presence of lauric acid, this broken sponge-like calcite (2–4 μm size) transformed to ellipsoid-like vaterite phase composed of nanocrystallites (Fig. 1b). After 24 h of growth, ellipsoid like microspheres of size 800 nm–1 μm appeared at low molar ratio of [Ca²⁺]/[LA] : 100. The size was found to have decreased to 600–900 nm on increasing the molar ratio of [Ca²⁺]/[LA] to 10. Growth of calcium carbonate was carefully examined at different time intervals at mole ratio of [Ca²⁺]/[LA] : 10. Crystals were isolated after 6 h, 12 h, 24 h and examined through SEM. Calcium carbonate nanospheres of size 40–80 nm, sub-micron spheres of 100–150 nm and 600–900 nm appeared after 6 h, 12 h and 24 h of growth, respectively (Fig. 2). As shown in Fig. 3, amorphous flower shaped morpho-

Fig. 2. SEM images of CaCO₃ growth in presence of lauric acid (mole ratios [M]/[L] = 10) at (a) 6 h, (b) 12 h, (c) 24 h, (d) enlarged picture of 24 h growth.

logy of CaCO₃ : La³⁺, CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ resulted after doping the rare-earth elements into CaCO₃ in presence of lauric acid at molar ratio of [Ln³⁺]/[LA] : 10. Existence of La³⁺ and Tb³⁺ in CaCO₃ was evident by EDAX spectrum (Fig. 3b, 3d).

Fig. 3. SEM images of metal carbonates produced in presence of lauric acid (mole ratios [M]/[L] = 10); (a) CaCO₃ : La³⁺, (b) EDAX spectrum of CaCO₃ : La³⁺, (c) CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺, (d) EDAX spectrum of CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺.

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns at 22.65, 29.08, 35.60, 38.95, 42.80, 47.10, 48.07, 57.08 (calcite) and 24.48, 32.47, 38.24, 44.62, 49.59, 56.17 (vaterite) confirmed the calcium carbonate phases produced under different experimental conditions (Fig. 4a, 4b). Non-crystalline powder patterns of CaCO₃ : La³⁺, CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ are shown in Fig. 4c, 4d.

Fig. 5 shows IR spectra of the hydrophobic CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ synthesized using lauric acid. The characteristic peaks at 2512, 1416, 874, 745 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum are attributed to the vaterite phase of CaCO₃. The peaks close to 2924 and 2852 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of lauric acid on the surface of carbonates (Fig. 5a, 5b, 5d). Additionally, the peak observed at 1082 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of above mentioned compounds is assigned to the Ca-O bond of calcium laurate^{13,22}. The above data was compared with calcium carbonate produced in control experiments (Fig. 5c).

Fig. 4. Powder XRD patterns of CaCO₃ produced in control experiments (a); CaCO₃ (b), CaCO₃ : La³⁺ (c), CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ (d) produced in presence of lauric acid (mole ratios [M]/[L] = 10) (c = calcite, v = vaterite).

Fig. 5. FT-IR spectra of (a) CaCO₃ : La³⁺, (b) CaCO₃ and (d) CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ produced in the presence of lauric acid; (c) CaCO₃ produced in control experiments.

TGA analysis revealed that the CaCO₃ prepared using lauric acid contained a thin layer of both calcium laurate and lauric acid around the particles. Fig. 6a, shows the % weight loss of CaCO₃ prepared with and without lauric acid, indicating that CaCO₃ (calcite phase) prepared without lauric acid in control experiments was stable up to 600 °C and decomposed to CaO and CO₂ by losing 44% of weight (Initial sample weight is 7.572 mg). The CaCO₃ synthesized in presence of lauric acid (Fig. 6b) exhibited a weight loss of 27% at a temperature below 300 °C. This weight loss may possibly be attributed to the decomposition of lauric acid and calcium laurate. The same is confirmed by FT-IR peaks at 2924, 2852, 1082 cm⁻¹. Vaterite phase of calcium carbonate decomposed to CaO and CO₂

in the region 300 to 600 °C (Initial sample weight is 10.347 mg).

Fig. 6. TGA spectrum of CaCO₃ produced in (a) control and (b) presence of lauric acid.

Superhydrophobic nature :

The hydrophobic nature of organically modified CaCO₃ was investigated through water contact angle measurement. Change in the surface characteristics of CaCO₃ after modification with lauric acid was done by sessile drop method using Phoenix, SEO, Korea. The prepared sample was pressed into a thin uniform layer on to a double sided adhesive tape stuck to a glass plate. As per earlier reports, contact angles of 103°, 122° and 91–140° have been reported for CaCO₃ treated with stearic acid²², oleic acid²³ and lauric acid¹³, respectively. It has been reported that the most important factor in determining the oleophobic properties of films of fatty acids, and similar polar organic compounds, adsorbed on solid surfaces was the density of the adsorbed molecules on the surfaces²⁴. In the present investigation, the value of water contact angle at 140°, as shown in Fig. 7, suggests superhydrophobic nature of CaCO₃ modified with lauric acid. The plausible explanation put forth for this behaviour is that during the growth of the material, COOH groups of lauric acid are directed towards Ca²⁺ ions whereas the long chain alkyl groups direct away resulting in hydrophobic behaviour.

Absorption properties :

Absorption of oil and genotoxic solvents by CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺, CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ was investigated according to Sarkar *et al.*¹³ (Fig. 8). Sunflower oil was selected to test the absorption properties of above metal carbon-

Fig. 7. Water contact angle of hydrophobic CaCO_3 .

ates. PTCDA was added to the oil to impart red colour (Fig. 8a). The absorption of xylene and toluene by synthesized carbonates was also investigated. The ratio of organic solvent to water was fixed at 1 : 10 wt% to measure the absorption efficiency. The synthesized CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ exhibited 100, 69.2 and 35.2% oil absorbing efficiency, respectively. Furthermore, these materials also displayed selective absorption of xylene and toluene. CaCO_3 showed 70.5 and 79.9% absorption efficiency for xylene and toluene, respectively. $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ absorb 21.0 and 23.5% of xylene and toluene, respectively. Similarly $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ exhibited 50.0% and 56.0% absorption efficiency for xylene and toluene, re-

Fig. 8. Absorption of oil (a) dispersion of PTCDA-dye in oil layer, (b and c) absorption of oil by CaCO_3 .

spectively. Relatively CaCO_3 displayed better absorption efficiency as compared to mixed metal carbonates. This may be explained on the basis of hydrophobic behaviour of lauric acid coated CaCO_3 in which the long chain alkyl groups direct away from Ca^{2+} ions towards non-polar substrate like oil and genotoxic solvents, thereby resulting in removal of the same. The data is presented in Table 1. Regeneration and recycling of spent adsorbent material as well as recovery of the oil is reported in the literature^{25,26}. As per our preliminary reports, spent lauric acid coated calcium carbonate could be regenerated by chemical extraction with petroleum ether.

Photoluminescence :

Luminescence property of lanthanide carbonates was also investigated. The La^{3+} ions with unfilled 4f orbitals in lanthanide carbonates do not possess luminescence. But as shown in Fig. 9a the blue emission at 485 nm by $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ after excitation at 365 nm, could be attributed to $n-\pi^*$ transition from La^{3+} ²⁷. Whereas, $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ emitted green emission particularly at 545 nm on photo excitation at 365 cm^{-1} (Fig. 9b) corresponding to the transition of $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_5$ from Tb^{3+} ions.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained from Merck. $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{TbCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, pyrylene-3,4,9,10-tetra carboxylic dianhydride (PTCDA) dye were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

Synthesis of minerals :

Synthesis of hydrophobic calcium carbonate was carried out by taking 0.147 g (1.0 mM) of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and different concentrations of lauric acid (0.01 mM, 0.02 mM and 0.1 mM) dissolved in 15 ml methanol in separate glass beakers. It was thoroughly stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. Each solution was then transferred into petri dishes and covered with parafilm having 2 to 3 holes in it to allow carbon dioxide to enter into the solution via vapour diffusion. The parafilm covered petri dishes were then placed in a desiccator containing ammonium carbonate (CO_2 source). After 24 h, the crystals appeared in the petri dishes were filtered and washed several times with methanol. In case of rare-earth doped calcium carbonates,

Table 1. Oil, toluene and xylene absorption efficiency of hydrophobic CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ samples in oil-water mixture (1 : 10)^a

Sl. no.	Sample name	Name of oil or organic solvent	Wt. of recovered water (g)	Wt. of absorbed oil/organic solvent (g)	Absorption efficiency (%)
1.	CaCO ₃	Sunflower oil	4.4	0.46	100
2.	CaCO ₃ : La ³⁺	Sunflower oil	4.3	0.32	69.5
3.	CaCO ₃ : Tb ³⁺	Sunflower oil	4.3	0.30	35.2
4.	CaCO ₃	<i>Ortho</i> xylene	4.4	0.31	70.5
5.	Ca-LaCO ₃	<i>Ortho</i> xylene	4.2	0	21
6.	Ca-TbCO ₃	<i>Ortho</i> xylene	4.3	0.22	50
7.	CaCO ₃	Toluene	4.4	0.348	79.9
8.	CaCO ₃ : La ³⁺	Toluene	4.4	0	23.5
9.	CaCO ₃ : Tb ³⁺	Toluene	4.3	0.24	56

^aTotal volume of oil/organic solvent-water mixture was 5 mL; 0.5 g of CaCO₃/CaCO₃ : La³⁺/CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ was added in each case.

Fig. 9. Photoluminescence spectrum of (a) CaCO₃ : La³⁺ (inset : optical microscopic picture of material under UV light), (b) CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ (inset : optical microscopic picture of material under UV light).

0.147 g (1.0 mM) of CaCl₂·2H₂O along with 0.4332 g (1.0 mM) La(NO₃)₃·6H₂O or 0.3734 g (1.0 mM) TbCl₃·6H₂O was used.

Absorption of oils and solvents :

Commercially available sunflower oil mixed with

pyrylene-3,4,9,10-tetra carboxylic dianhydride (PTCDA) dye was used for the oil absorption study. Mixture was prepared by adding 10 mg of PTCDA dye to oil and water in 1 : 10 ratio. To this mixture 500 mg hydrophobic carbonate (CaCO₃/CaCO₃ : La³⁺/CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺) sample was added to test the absorption of oil.

Characterisation techniques :

The morphology of products was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using FEI Quanta 200 FEG with EDS. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was recorded on “PANALYTICAL X’Pertpro Powder X-ray diffractometer” with graphite monochromatic CuK_α (λ = 1.5406 Å) radiation at room temperature. Size of the calcium carbonate particles was measured by Dynamic Light Scattering technique (SZ100, Nanopartica, Horiba Scientific). The infrared spectrum was recorded using KBr pellet preparation method on a Perkin-Elmer “spectrum two FT-IR” system. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using “Melter Toledo TGA/DSC-1” apparatus in the temperature range between 25 and 800 °C under N₂ with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. Luminescence spectrum of solid sample was recorded with “Perkin-Elmer LS-55 Luminescence Spectrometer” at room temperature.

Conclusions

Synthesis of superhydrophobic CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ was investigated at room temperature in lauric acid medium. Especially, the morphology, absorption and optical properties were examined with influ-

ence of lauric acid and lanthanide dopants. After doping lanthanide elements into CaCO₃, spherical particles transformed to flower-like morphology. The FT-IR spectra and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the samples confirmed the presence of lauric acid on the surface of the synthesized carbonates. The water contact angle at 140° suggested the formation of superhydrophobic materials. CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ which displayed absorption of oil and genotoxic organic solvents such as xylene and toluene from an oil/organic solvent-water mixture. Further, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ exhibited blue luminescence and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ emitted green luminescence on photo excitation at 365 nm.

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